

Eco-friendly synthesis of amides and their microbial activity

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Manuscript received online 23 July 2014, accepted 18 August 2014

Abstract : A series of *N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-phenoxy-3-phenylacrylamide 5a-e, 1-morpholino-2-phenoxy-3-phenyl prop-2-ene-1-one 7a-e and 2-phenoxy-3-phenyl-*N*-(4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide 9a-e were synthesized, characterized and screened for their microbial activities. All these compounds were prepared by conventional and microwave assisted methods from corresponding acrylic acids and amines. All amide derivatives prepared by microwave irradiation method gave higher yield and took less time. Amide derivatives were screened for their microbial activity against different bacteria viz. *Ensifer* sp. (LSR 3), *Pseudomonas* sp. (PGPR 3), *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The results of antibacterial screening revealed that some of the synthesized amide derivatives exhibited poor inhibition against *Ensifer* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *S. aureus* and *E. coli* while remaining compounds displayed mild to moderate antibacterial activity. Maximum degree of inhibition (zone 20 mm) was shown by the compounds containing triazole moiety against *E. coli*.

Keywords : Environmentally benign, α,β -unsaturated acids, boric acid, acrylamides, microwave, microbial activity.

Introduction

Amide linkages are present in a number of natural products and are responsible for their biological activity. Therefore, the formation of amide bond is important to both synthetic chemists and biologists. Approximately 66% of all preliminary screening reactions in medicinal chemistry laboratories involve amide formation¹. A plethora of procedures for the formation of carboxamides is presented in the literature. The most explored method incorporates acid chlorides as electrophiles that react with the amines in the presence of an acid scavenger. Despite its versatility, this method has some limitations because there are many unstable acid chlorides and also require hazardous reagents for their preparation (thionyl chloride, oxalyl chloride and phosgene etc.). The concerned disadvantages categorize these methods as uneco-friendly and warrant the development of a catalytic and mild process for amidation. Ishihara *et al.* reported the first boron reagent based catalytic method that allows direct amide formation from free carboxylic acids and amines as the

reaction partners². A phenylboronic acid derivative bearing electron-withdrawing substituents in the *m*- and *p*-positions was found to be the catalyst of choice for these kinds of transformations. Tang *et al.* featured the use of cheap, readily available, nontoxic and eco-friendly boric acid, B(OH)₃, as highly effective catalyst, which proved to be superior to other known catalysts involved in the amidation process³.

Microwave irradiation is used for a variety of organic transformations where in chemical reactions are accelerated because of selective absorption of microwave energy by polar and non-polar molecules. An efficient and environment friendly synthetic method for the synthesis of primary amides under microwave irradiation was described, in which the primary amine was directly reacted with acid without using any catalytic agent. The reaction took place in 7–21 min, which was much shorter than the conventional methods, with excellent yields^{4,5}.

To our surprise, despite the proven potential of boric acid as a catalyst and microwave it has not been explored

extensively for amidation. Therefore keeping in view the importance of above mentioned methods without hazardous effects on environment, the present work was carried out to synthesize acrylamides having heterocyclic moiety as microbial agents which could afford better therapeutic results.

Results and discussion

Different substituted benzaldehydes **1a-e** were made to undergo Knoevenagel condensation reaction with phenoxyacetic acid **2** in the presence of sodium ethoxide (Scheme 1) to yield corresponding acrylic acids⁶ **3a-e** whose structures were confirmed by FT-IR. The prepared α,β -unsaturated acids were reacted with 4-aminophenazone **4**, morpholine **6** and 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole **8** in the pres-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

ence of boric acid (act as catalyst) to give corresponding amides⁶ (**5a-e**, **7a-e**, **9a-e**) (Scheme 2). The FT-IR spectra of acrylic acids showed absorption in the range of 3080–3138 (O-H stretching), 1080–1089 (C-O-C stretching), 1680–1693 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching). The absence of absorption band at 1700–1750 cm^{-1} and appearance of it at 1619–1634 cm^{-1} confirms the conversion of aldehyde to C=C group. The synthesized acrylamides showed characteristic absorption of 3422–3450 (N-H stretching), 1613–1664 (C=O stretching), 1596–1630 (C=C stretching) and 1257–1261 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretching) in IR spectra. The ¹H NMR spectra showed a singlet in the range of δ 6.81–6.88 due to hydrogen of =C-H, singlet δ 8.15–10.02 due to hydrogen of -NH. The appearance of multiplet at δ 6.83–8.76 was due to aromatic protons. Moreover, ¹³C NMR showed the signals in the range of δ 114.1–119.5 and at δ 158.5–172.2 due to =CH and O=C-NH carbon respectively. Physical data (yield, melting point, state and color) of acids and amides were determined. FT-IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR results were in agreement with the proposed structures.

All the amide derivatives were also prepared by mi-

crowave irradiation method and these were confirmed by TLC, color, physical state and melting points. The perusal of data presented in Table 1 revealed that the product yield was increased by 11–42% with the use of microwave irradiation method. Even the reaction took only 7–21 min in microwave irradiation method that took 14 h to complete in boric acid catalyzed method.

then spread on the specific medium plates. Sterile filter paper discs moistened with test compound solution in DMSO were carefully placed on the medium inoculated with the specific bacterial suspension. Sterile filter paper discs dipped in DMSO served as control. These plates were incubated at 28 ± 1 °C and the diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm) was measured after 24 h. The growth

Table 1. Physical parameters and comparison of methods of amides

Compd.	Molecular formula	Color	Melting point (°C)	R_f value	Yield (%)			Time taken in MW method (min)
					Conventional method	MW method	Increase in yield (%)	
5a	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃	Off-white	191–192	0.72	47	89	42	19
7a	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ NO ₃	Off-white	119–120	0.70	52	90	38	15
9a	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	Off-white	150–151	0.67	65	87	22	11
5b	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	Off-white	166–167	0.68	48	82	36	13
7b	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ NO ₃ Cl	Off-white	131–132	0.63	75	86	11	21
9b	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	Off-white	172–173	0.69	70	86	16	7
5c	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	Off-white	217–218	0.60	50	70	20	11
7c	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ NO ₃ Cl	Off-white	160–161	0.65	70	84	14	7
9c	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	White	143–144	0.60	67	80	13	17
5d	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅	Brown	205–206	0.65	56	74	18	8
7d	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	Light brown	209–210	0.60	45	68	23	18
9d	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	Brown	182–183	0.70	61	85	24	12
5e	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅	Yellow	160–161	0.71	43	73	30	16
7e	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	Light brown	102–103	0.73	50	84	34	15
9e	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	Off-white	115–116	0.60	68	88	20	18

Antimicrobial testing :

All the synthesized amide derivatives viz. (**5a-e**, **7a-e**, **9a-e**) were screened for their inhibitory effect on the growth of four bacterial species viz. *Ensifer* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* at various concentrations. The primary screening was carried out using the bacterial sensitivity-filter paper disc method using Congo red yeast extract mannitol agar (CRYEMA) medium for *Ensifer* sp., King's B medium for *Pseudomonas* sp. and Nutrient Agar for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Agar medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 psi and 121 °C for twenty minutes. The plates were prepared by pouring 15–20 mL of the sterilized media into sterilized petriplates. Media was then allowed to solidify and stored for 2 days to ensure sterility. Suspension of 3–4 days old broth of test organism was

of the organism on medium containing the test compound was also compared with the growth on the plates containing micro-organism without test compound that is control with unaided eye.

The results of antibacterial screening of all the newly synthesized compounds are presented in Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5. The results revealed that the some of synthesized amide derivatives showed no inhibition against *Ensifer* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Maximum *Ensifer* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **7b**, **7c**, **9c** and **9e** showing inhibition zone 12–13 mm. Maximum *Pseudomonas* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **5a**, **5d** and **7d** showing inhibition zone 14 mm. Maximum *S. aureus* growth was inhibited by compounds **9e** showing inhibition zone 14 mm. Maximum *E. coli* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **9b** and **9d** showing

Table 2. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Ensifer* sp. at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Compds.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)					
	5000	4000	3000	2000	1000	500
5a	11	10	9.5	9	8.5	0
7a	10.5	10	10	10	9	0
9a	11.5	11.5	11	10	9.5	0
5b	10	8	0	0	0	0
7b	12	11	10.5	8	7.5	0
9b	11	10	8	7	6	0
5c	10	9	9	8	8	0
7c	13	12.5	11	10	8.5	0
9c	12	11	10	9	8	0
5d	0	0	0	0	0	0
7d	11	10	10	9	8	0
9d	9	0	0	0	0	0
5e	10	10	10	10	10	0
7e	0	0	0	0	0	0
9e	12	11.5	10	0	0	0
Ampicillin	20	18	16.5	16	15	14

Table 3. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Pseudomonas* sp. at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Compds.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)					
	5000	4000	3000	2000	1000	500
5a	14	12.5	11	11	10	0
7a	0	0	0	0	0	0
9a	11	10	10	9.5	9	0
5b	12.5	11	10	10	8	0
7b	13	10	10	8	7	0
9b	11	10	10	0	0	0
5c	13	12	11.5	10	9	0
7c	11	10	9.4	8	6.5	0
9c	12	11	10	9	8	0
5d	14	11	9	8	7	0
7d	14	13	12	10.5	8	0
9d	0	0	0	0	0	0
5e	10	10	10	10	10	0
7e	13	11	11	11	10	0
9e	12	9.5	9	8	8	0
Ampicillin	24	20	18	16.5	15	13

inhibition zone 20 mm. The compound **9b** showed exceptionally good behaviour with the inhibition zone of 12 mm which was even more than standard having 10 mm zone.

Table 4. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *S. aureus* at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Compds.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)						
	5000	4000	3000	2000	1000	500	250
5a	11.5	10	9	8	0	0	0
7a	0	0	11	10	7	0	0
9a	11	10.5	9	8	0	0	0
5b	11	10	10	9	8.5	0	0
7b	12	9	8	10	10	0	0
9b	12.5	10	9	8	8	7.5	7
5c	10	10	9	8.5	6	0	0
7c	11	10	9	8	8	7.5	0
9c	11	10	9	9	8	7	0
5d	11	10.5	10	10	10	9	0
7d	8	11	10	9	8	7	0
9d	11	10	10	9	9	6	0
5e	12	9	9	8	8	6	0
7e	11	10	10	10	9	9	0
9e	14	13	13	13	12	8	6.5
Ampicillin	26	18	18	17	14	12	9

Table 5. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *E. coli* at different concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Compds.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)						
	5000	4000	3000	2000	1000	500	250
5a	12	10	9.5	8	8	6.5	0
7a	10	10	10	10	10	0	0
9a	12	11	11	11	10	9	0
5b	11	11	10	9	8	7	0
7b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9b	20	12	12	12	12	7.5	0
5c	13	12	11.5	11	11	9	0
7c	19	14	10	12	6.5	0	0
9c	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5d	16	12	8	0	0	0	0
7d	15	14	13	12	10	7	0
9d	20	12	12	12	11	0	0
5e	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7e	15	14	13	12	10	7	0
9e	12	11	9	8	8	7	0
Ampicillin	24	20	16	14	10	8	7.5

Similar results were also reported by Kaur *et al.*⁵, Kooner *et al.*⁷ and Kalirajan *et al.*⁸. This inhibition may be attributed to substitution of nitro and chloro group on phenyl ring. So overall it was observed that the com-

pounds having morpholine and phenazone moiety exhibited less growth inhibitory effect as compared to compounds with triazole moiety which inhibit the growth of bacteria to large extent.

Experimental

General :

Open capillaries method was used to determine the melting points and is uncorrected. The structures of acids and amide derivatives were confirmed by spectroscopic analysis. FT-IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were got scanned from Central Instrumentation Laboratories (CIL), Punjab University, Chandigarh. Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer was used for recording IR spectra using KBr discs and Bruker Avance II 100 MHz was used for recording ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra using TMS as an internal standard. The chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm) values and the abbreviations 's' and 'm' stand for singlet and multiplet respectively. The purity of compounds was checked on silica gel G coated TLC plates and the visualization was done in iodine chamber.

General procedure for the preparation of acrylic acid :

An equimolar mixture of phenoxyacetic acid (**2**, 0.05 mole, 7.6 g), substituted benzaldehyde (**1a-e**, 0.05 mole) and sodium ethoxide (0.05 mole, 3.4 g) were placed in round bottomed flask equipped with a reflux condenser carrying calcium chloride guard tube. Ethyl alcohol (15 ml) was added to the above reaction mixture and refluxed for 11 h in an oil bath. After cooling to ambient temperature, the above reaction mixture was acidified with glacial acetic acid and filtered to obtain the precipitates which were recrystallised from ethyl alcohol and hot water to get the pure respective acrylic acid. Absence of spot of aldehyde on thin layer chromatographic plates revealed the purity of acid.

2-Phenoxy-3-phenyl acrylic acid (**3a**) :

IR (KBr) : 3103 (O-H), 1680 (C=O), 1619 (C=C), 1426 (O-H bending), 1312 (C-O), 1294 (C-O-Ar asymmetric), 1080 (C-O-Ar symmetric), 970 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending).

3-(2-Chloro phenyl)-2-phenoxy acrylic acid (**3b**) :

IR (KBr) : 3109 (O-H), 1671 (C=O), 1625 (C=C), 1426 (O-H bending), 1323 (C-O), 1295 (C-O-Ar asymmetric), 1227 (C-Cl), 1083 (C-O-Ar symmetric), 970 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending).

3-(4-Chloro phenyl)-2-phenoxy acrylic acid (**3c**) :

IR (KBr) : 3115 (O-H), 1680 (C=O), 1628 (C=C), 1429 (O-H bending), 1331 (C-O), 1298 (C-O-Ar asymmetric), 1220 (C-Cl), 1084 (C-O-Ar symmetric), 970 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending).

3-(2-Nitro phenyl)-2-phenoxy acrylic acid (**3d**) :

IR (KBr) : 3134 (O-H), 1645 (C=O), 1617 (C=C), 1435 (O-H bending), 1333 (C-O), 1288 (C-O-Ar asymmetric), 1280 (N=O), 1084 (C-O-Ar symmetric), 977 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending).

3-(3-Nitro phenyl)-2-phenoxy acrylic acid (**3e**) :

IR (KBr) : 3140 (O-H), 1649 (C=O), 1621 (C=C), 1443 (O-H bending), 1338 (C-O), 1289 (C-O-Ar asymmetric), 1285 (N=O), 1089 (C-O-Ar symmetric), 979 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending).

General procedure for the preparation of amide derivatives :

Conventional method :

To a solution of acrylic acid (**3a-e**, 0.03 mole) in toluene (80 ml) taken in a round bottomed flask was added boric acid (0.30 mmole) and was stirred at room temperature to make a clear solution. Amine (0.03 mole) was added to it in one installment and the reaction mixture was refluxed at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 14 h in an oil bath. Approximately 0.5 ml water was trapped in Dean-Stark apparatus. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then it was poured to hexane (400 ml) with constant stirring and precipitates separated out immediately. The stirring was continued for additional 30 min. The precipitates were filtered and then dried at room temperature to get amide. Thin layer chromatography technique was used to check the purity of amide.

Microwave irradiation method :

The conventionally prepared acrylic acid (**3a-e**, 0.01 mole) was taken in a 50 ml beaker. Amine (0.01 mole) was added to it and mixed well. The mixture was irradi-

ated in microwave oven at 180 W for different time interval. The progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography at an interval of one minute. After the completion of reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and was filtered off. It was recrystallized from methanol to furnish corresponding acrylamide.

N-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-phenoxy-3-phenyl acrylamide (**5a**) :

IR (KBr) : 3432 (N-H), 3054 (Ar C-H), 2918 (C-H), 1647 (C=O), 1600 (C=C), 1429 (C-N), 1261 (C-O-Ar), 963 (=C-H bending), 757 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 2.77 (3H, s), N-CH₃ 3.37 (3H, s), =C-H 6.81 (1H, s), ArH 6.83–7.43 (15H, m), NH 8.15 (s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 11.1, N-CH₃ 35.9, =C-H 114.4, =C-O-Ar 152, C-O-C=C 157.6, O=C-NH₂ 161.4, ArC 114.6–135.5.

3-(2-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-phenoxyacrylamide (**5b**) :

IR (KBr) : 3440 (N-H), 3059 (Ar C-H), 2916 (C-H), 1649 (C=O), 1604 (C=C), 1425 (C-N), 1257 (C-O-Ar), 1172 (C-Cl), 932 (=C-H bending), 754 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 2.17 (3H, s), N-CH₃ 2.81 (3H, s), =C-H 6.88 (1H, s), ArH 6.90–7.46 (15H, m), NH 8.30 (s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 11.1, N-CH₃ 35.8, =C-H 114.4, =C-O-Ar 152.4, C-O-C=C 156.8, O=C-NH₂ 161.4, ArC 119.6–135.6.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-phenoxyacrylamide (**5c**) :

IR (KBr) : 3443 (N-H), 3052 (Ar C-H), 2920 (C-H), 1652 (C=O), 1619 (C=C), 1430 (C-N), 1261 (C-O-Ar), 1174 (C-Cl), 938 (=C-H bending), 756 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 2.53 (3H, s), N-CH₃ 3.36 (3H, s), =C-H 6.81 (1H, s), ArH 6.83–7.22 (15H, m), NH 8.16 (s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 11.1, N-CH₃ 35.9, =C-H 114.3, =C-O-Ar 151.9, C-O-C=C 157.6, O=C-NH₂ 167.2, ArC 114.5–134.8.

N-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(2-nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxyacrylamide (**5d**) :

IR (KBr) : 3448 (N-H), 3057 (Ar C-H), 2919 (C-H), 1660 (C=O), 1628 (C=C), 1495 (N=O), 1427 (C-N), 1259 (C-O-Ar), 972 (=C-H bending), 757 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 2.48 (3H, s), N-CH₃ 3.20 (3H, s), =C-H 7.26 (1H, s), ArH 7.27–8.14

(15H, m), NH 10.02 (s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 11.1, N-CH₃ 34.9, =C-H 114.3, =C-O-Ar 152.4, C-O-C=C 158.6, O=C-NH₂ 161.4, ArC 114.5–135.6.

N-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxyacrylamide (**5e**) :

IR (KBr) : 3384 (N-H), 3055 (Ar C-H), 2920 (C-H), 1664 (C=O), 1630 (C=C), 1491 (N=O), 1415 (C-N), 1261 (C-O-Ar), 955 (=C-H bending), 757 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 2.53 (3H, s), N-CH₃ 3.21 (3H, s), =C-H 7.26 (1H, s), ArH 7.33–8.76 (15H, m), NH 9.8 (s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₃ 9.9, N-CH₃ 35.1, =C-H 114.3, =C-O-Ar 152.2, C-O-C=C 158.3, O=C-NH₂ 170.9, ArC 115.9–139.3.

1-Morpholino-2-phenoxy-3-phenyl prop-2-ene-1-one (**7a**) :

IR (KBr) : 3056 (Ar C-H), 2918 (-CH₂-), 1640 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1427 (C-N), 1045 (C-O), 961 cm⁻¹ (=C-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₂ 3.69 (8H, s), =C-H 6.84 (1H, s), ArH 6.88–7.91 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ N-CH₂ 44.0, N-CH₂ 65.2, =C-H 114.3, =C-O-Ar 145.6, O=C-NH₂ 158.5, ArC 119.9–131.1.

3-(2-Chlorophenyl)-1-morpholino-2-phenoxy prop-2-ene-1-one (**7b**) :

IR (KBr) : 3056 (Ar C-H), 2955 (-CH₂-), 1645 (C=O), 1608 (C=C), 1426 (C-N), 1174 (C-Cl), 1045 (C-O), 961 cm⁻¹ (=C-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₂ 4.33 (8H, s), =C-H 6.85 (1H, s), ArH 6.87–7.24 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ N-CH₂ 44.2, N-CH₂ 70.7, =C-H 119.5, =C-O-Ar 144.3, O=C-NH₂ 163.7, ArC 125.1–134.0.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1-morpholino-2-phenoxy prop-2-ene-1-one (**7c**) :

IR (KBr) : 3056 (Ar C-H), 2918 (-CH₂-), 1618 (C=O), 1596 (C=C), 1426 (C-N), 1178 (C-Cl), 1104 (C-O), 978 cm⁻¹ (=C-H bending); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH₂ 4.25 (8H, s), =C-H 6.83 (1H, s), ArH 6.85–7.23 (10, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO) : δ N-CH₂ 43.3, N-CH₂ 64.5, =C-H 114.2, =C-O-Ar 146.5, O=C-NH₂ 172.2 ArC 119.9–130.6.

1-Morpholino-3-(2-nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxy prop-2-ene-1-one (**7d**) :

IR (KBr) : 3057 (Ar C-H), 2918 (-CH₂-), 1620 (C=O), 1603 (C=C), 1494 (N=O), 1427 (C-N), 1104 (C-O),

961 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH_2 4.38 (8H, s), =C-H 6.88 (1H, s), ArH 6.90–7.92 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ N- CH_2 43.8, N- CH_2 66.9, =C-H 114.2, =C-O-Ar 151.6, O=C-NH₂ 171.6, ArC 119.8–131.3.

1-Morpholino-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxy prop-2-ene-1-one (7e) :

IR (KBr) : 3056 (Ar C-H), 2952 (-CH₂-), 1616 (C=O), 1601 (C=C), 1494 (N=O), 1427 (C-N), 1108 (C-O), 935 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ CH_2 4.22 (8H, s), =C-H 6.82 (1H, s), ArH 6.84–7.22 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ N- CH_2 43.8, N- CH_2 66.2, =C-H 114.3, =C-O-Ar 147.6, O=C-NH₂ 171.4, ArC 119.8–136.1.

2-Phenoxy-3-phenyl-N-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide (9a) :

IR (KBr) : 3422 (N-H), 3057 (Ar C-H), 2920 (C-H), 1625 (C=O), 1599 (C=C), 1542 (N-H bending), 1424 (C-N), 1261 (C-O-Ar), 934 (=C-H bending), 749 cm^{-1} (N-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 6.87 (1H, s), ArH 6.90–7.98 (15H, m), NH 7.99 (s), -CH=N 8.25 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 114.4, -CH=N 143.9, =C-O-Ar 144.5, O=C-NH₂ 171.6, ArC 119.6–128.9.

3-(2-Chlorophenyl)-2-phenoxy-N-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide (9b) :

IR (KBr) : 3426 (N-H), 3057 (Ar C-H), 2918 (C-H), 1648 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1427 (C-N), 1259 (C-O-Ar), 1180 (C-Cl), 978 (=C-H bending), 750 cm^{-1} (N-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 6.87 (1H, s), ArH 6.91–7.32 (15H, m), NH 8.26 (s), -CH=N 8.70 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 114.3, -CH=N 143.9, =C-O-Ar 144.8, O=C-NH₂ 171.6, ArC 120.1–129.3.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-phenoxy-N-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide (9c) :

IR (KBr) : 3428 (N-H), 3128 (Ar C-H), 2919 (C-H), 1652 (C=O), 1618 (C=C), 1427 (C-N), 1261 (C-O-Ar), 1174 (C-Cl), 978 (=C-H bending), 779 cm^{-1} (N-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 6.88 (1H, s), ArH 6.91–7.97 (15H, m), NH 8.24 (s), -CH=N 8.95 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 114.3, -CH=N 138.8, =C-O-Ar 143.9, O=C-NH₂ 171.2, ArC 120.1–130.8.

3-(2-Nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxy-N-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide (9d) :

IR (KBr) : 3057–3435 (N-H), 3128 (Ar C-H), 2919 (C-H), 1640 (C=O), 1602 (C=C), 1494 (N=O), 1427 (C-N), 1259 (C-O-Ar), 936 (=C-H bending), 750 cm^{-1} (N-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 6.83 (1H, s), ArH 6.91–7.97 (15H, m), NH 8.24 (s), -CH=N 8.33 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 114.1, -CH=N 143.8, =C-O-Ar 148.0, O=C-NH₂ 171.4, ArC 120.7–138.6.

3-(3-Nitrophenyl)-2-phenoxy-N-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-4-yl)acrylamide (9e) :

IR (KBr) : 3450 (N-H), 3057 (Ar C-H), 2920 (C-H), 1640 (C=O), 1620 (C=C), 1470 (N=O), 1426 (C-N), 1252 (C-O-Ar), 937 (=C-H bending), 749 cm^{-1} (N-H bending); ^1H NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 6.86 (1H, s), ArH 6.88–7.81 (15H, m), NH 8.26 (s), -CH=N 8.37 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO) : δ =C-H 114.1, -CH=N 143.7, =C-O-Ar 147.9, O=C-NH₂ 171.1, ArC 120.1–138.6.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Panjab University, Chandigarh for providing IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectral data of synthesized compounds.

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